

(44–55% males) in most species, but it was far from equality in *Macrosteles sexnotatus* (29% males), *Exitianus taeniaceps* (63% males), and *Falctoya aglauros*, and *Oliarus frontalis* (75% males each). **W**

Control of rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* with seedling root dip treatments

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An experiment conducted at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, in kharif 1976 evaluated the effectiveness of selected insecticides as root-dip treatment for controlling pests in newly transplanted rice. The trial was laid out with four insecticides – chlorpyrifos, chlorfenvinphos, dimethoate, and leptophos – at different concentrations and exposure times in a randomized design replicated four times, and

Percentage of leaves affected by thrips at 15 days after transplanting. Coimbatore, India.

Chemical concn (%)	Exposure time (h)	Leaves (%) affected ^a
<i>Chlorpyrifos 20 EC</i>		
0.02	2	14.6
0.02	4	13.9
0.02	12	13.9
0.04	2	12.1
0.4	4	9.6
<i>Chlorfenvinphos 24 EC</i>		
0.02	2	17.3
0.02	4	10.1
0.02	12	14.9
0.04	2	15.2
0.04	4	17.5
<i>Dimethoate 30 EC</i>		
0.02	2	21.5
0.02	4	7.8
0.02	12	13.1
0.04	2	12.8
0.4	4	11.2
<i>Leptophos 35 EC</i>		
0.02	2	10.4
0.02	4	13.0
0.02	12	20.2
0.4	2	17.2
0.04	4	14.9
<i>Control</i>		36.1

^aS.E. = 2.93%; C.D. = 8.64%. Average of four replications.

compared with an untreated control. The seedling roots were kept in the insecticide solutions for specified times before transplanting. Pests such as thrips, whorl maggots, and stem borers on five random plants per replication were recorded at 15,30, and 45 days after transplanting (DT).

All the insecticides significantly reduced thrip incidence at 15 DT. Chlorpyrifos at 0.04% for 4 hours was best, followed by dimethoate at 0.02% for 4 hours, and chlorfenvinphos at

0.02% for 4 hours. The whorl maggot was noticed only at 30 DT, but the incidence was low. However, the incidence was minimum in the chlorfenvinphos 0.02% treatment for 4 hours. In all treatments, stem borer incidence was less than that in the control at 30 DT, but increased by 45 DT. Although not extremely effective, seedling root dip with chlorpyrifos 0.04% or dimethoate 0.02% for 4 hours can be used to control thrips in the early transplanted crop. **W**

Ragged stunt virus disease in India and Sri Lanka

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During the International Rice Testing Program monitoring tour to South India and Sri Lanka in February 1978, rice plants with symptoms of ragged stunt virus disease—identical to those previously observed in the Philippines, Indonesia, and Thailand—were observed. Numerous TNAU breeding lines at the Paddy Breeding Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore,

India, were infected. At the Batalagoda Central Rice Breeding Station, Sri Lanka; only one plant of the variety BG 34-8 was observed to be infected. Transmission studies will be conducted by Indian and Sri Lankan scientists to confirm the reports.

Recent epidemics in Indonesia and the Philippines have brought ragged stunt to the attention of rice scientists. The presence of the disease in such widely separated geographical regions as Sri Lanka, India, the Philippines, Indonesia, and Thailand indicates that it has probably been endemic in Asia for years. **W**

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effects of herbicides on rice seed coated with activated carbon and direct seeded

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The performance of five granular herbicides in broadcast-flooded rice was evaluated in the second crop of 1977 at the Chiayi Station. Seed of the modem indica selection, Chianung-sen-yu 13 were coated with 8 kg activated carbon/ha before broadcasting on a flooded soil at the rate of 100 kg/ha. Mixed seeds of *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Cyperus difformis* were also

sown at 3 kg/ha immediately after the rice seed were broadcast. Herbicides were applied at 6 days after seeding, when most of the rice and weeds were at the one- to two-leaf stage.

Of the five granular herbicides (see table), Perfluidone/2,4-D IPE gave the best weed control. Benzglycereth (WL29226) gave the poorest control; the others controlled weeds satisfactorily. Coating rice seeds with activated carbon did not affect the effectiveness of herbicides, but it improved their selectivity to direct-seeded rice considerably. When activated carbon was used, rice toxicity ratings were reduced by almost a third in the less selective granular herbicides terbuchlor,